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EXPERT SYSTEM FOR ASSESSING
THE STATUS OF THE ACCESS CONTROL
SYSTEM TO THE INFORMATION
ENVIRONMENT OF SMART FACTORY

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It is considered the topical issues of access control systems risk assessment of a single information environment of the smart production management system in connection with the risks that arise as a result of using the Internet of things (IoT) as an integral part of the Industry 4.0 concept. The author considered the properties of the IoT architecture from the point of view of its information security when integrated with a production management system. The methodology for building an access control system using fuzzy logic, developed in the author's previous research, in which the author proposed and substantiated ideas for integrating various monitoring and intrusion detection systems in order to build an expert system, also found further practical development. In the paper, the information system is been considered from the point of view of system analysis as the interaction of subjects and objects of the system, the relationships between which are described by access control policies. This approach allows considering the real state of objects based on the system architecture and its vulnerability, changes in the system state over time, and to adjust access policies based on the level of risks assessed using the specified data. The methodology involves the use of modern tools and software, such as intrusion detection systems (IDS), fuzzy testing, user and entity behavior analytics (UEBA), user activity monitoring (UAM), software bill of material (SBOM), and machine learning approaches. Relevant libraries and databases: CIS benchmark, common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVEs), common platform enumeration (CPE) dictionary and common vulnerability scoring system (CVSS) are an integral part of the methodology, ensuring standardization and integration of the methodology with other approaches and methods of controlling and monitoring information systems. Particular attention has been paid to the issue of identifying vulnerabilities of robotic equipment and assessing their impact on production processes as a whole.

Keywords: access control system, intrusion detection system, user activity monitoring, common vulnerability scoring system, machine learning, IoT, smart factory, Industry 4.0.

Introduction

The Fourth industrial revolution (4IR or Industry 4.0) is a rapidly growing concept that involves widespread automation and digitization of production models using modern intelligent technologies. Like all previous technological revolutions, the fourth will significantly change people's lives both from the point of view of its quality and from the point of view of safety. The author's article is devoted to the consideration of information security issues and risks that will arise during the technological revolution.

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At the beginning of the study, it is very interesting to take a short excursion into the history of industrial automation, initiated by the outstanding scientist V.M. Glushkov, the famous developer of the theory of digital automata, the creator of multiprocessor macro-pipeline supercomputers, and the organizer of the Institute of Cybernetics of the Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

In 1958, V.M. Glushkov proposed the idea of creating a universal control machine. The transition from specialized control machines based on the technical basis of the first generation (tube) to universal semiconductor ones was important from the point of view of organizing their industrial production and widespread use in process control systems or automated control systems for technological preparation of production [1, 2].

In 1959, Viktor Mikhailovich began work on an interesting new project to automate the moving (motor) function of robots. At the same time, primitive vision was added to it, capable of perceiving only the position of the instrument needle or the scale division [3].

This short excursion is very interesting from the point of view of the practical development of Glushkov's ideas, laid down in the distant 50s of the last century in the modern ideology of smart production, which involves the combination of production equipment, information systems, the Internet of things (IoT) and artificial intelligence. It is the combination of a robot and computer vision for its control that we will encounter in one of the modern architectures of smart production later in the article.

The reason for the emergence of a number of risks is the very nature of the fourth technological revolution, which involves the merging of automated production, data exchange and production technologies into a single information and cognitive system using the principles and approaches of big data processing and artificial intelligence. A new approach to the organization of the added value chain based on the synergy obtained from the combination of information systems, the IoT and the Internet of services (IoS) within the concept of smart enterprises puts forward new requirements for data acquisition and processing.

Industry 4.0 involves receiving and processing data from various technological and information systems, which, on the one hand, allows making quick decisions and improving technological and management processes, and on the other hand, from the point of view of the heterogeneity of information and data, requires the use of more intelligent and secure methods of data processing [4, 5].

As a rule, various studies distinguish the following key components of Industry 4.0 [6, 7].

- The cyber-physical system is built-in computer and network technologies that allow you to observe and control the process of physical production and receive feedback.
- Internet of things — a combination of various components (sensors, smartphones, etc.) via the Internet, which enables their interaction with each other to achieve common goals.
- Internet of services — provision of services by suppliers via the Internet.

A smart factory is a factory where the equipment is automated, controlled by information technologies and can receive feedback about the state of the object in physical space using sensors.

The author of the article would not single out the «smart factory» component separately, since it is essentially the result of the fourth industrial revolution. Obviously, as a component, we can consider shifting the emphasis to big data, which accumulates very quickly thanks to the use of IoT and IoS technologies. It is big data and the IoT that are becoming a challenge for many companies from the point of view of information security.

Let us consider the main technologies of the fourth technological revolution such as IoT technology, radio frequency identification (rFID), robotics, augmented and virtual reality, 3D printing and big data.

The IoT technology, which are designed to unite the physical and digital worlds, has radically changed many sectors of the economy. Billions of devices have already been connected to each other, which provides the aforementioned advantages in terms of speed of decision-making, but also leads to new challenges from the point of view of cyber security. Against this background, identification technologies such as RFID enable the connection of the world of the IoT and the production environment, which in turn could also be virtualized with the help of digital twins.

RFID is an important source of data for the Internet of things, which creates an ecosystem for real-time monitoring of the state of objects and systems, which allows for quick and optimal decisions after effective processing of the received streams of unstructured and unscalable data. In a broad sense, radio frequency identification is a component that unites the technologies of Industry 4.0.

Robotics is constantly evolving, and industrial robots specifically designed to both perform typical operations independently and interact with humans will be key to the industry of the future. Robotics combines knowledge from various fields of science and technology, and in turn serves as a source of their development.

Augmented and virtual reality are technologies that combine the real world with the digital one. It became possible to create realistic images, sounds and other images, as well as transmit images, control signals and information over long distances and implement modern methodologies, for example, in medicine, sports, the military, etc.

Big data has already been mentioned in the article — it is data, the collection, management and processing of which cannot be carried out with the help of hardware environments and software tools that are most often used, within the time allowed for the user. These problems pose a certain challenge and retard the process of digital industrialization. On the one hand, the amount of data that appears during a work shift is hundreds or even thousands of times more than it was ten years ago thanks to IoT, on the other hand, the question of processing this data and its normalization arises due to its unstructured nature, diversity, volumes and accumulation rate.

The development of prototypes and their testing, as well as the launch of small series of test products, become fast and economically justified with the help of 3D printing. This technology is becoming increasingly important in design, architecture, engineering and other fields.

Thus, the development of IoT in industry is determined by the fourth industrial revolution, where modern concepts of a smart enterprise (factory, plant) were reflected in the practical implementation of modern automated production [7, 8].

Considering the fact that the number of IoT devices is increasing at a tremendous pace and by 2025 it is predicted that more than 75 billion IoT devices will be used, the issue of developing effective access control systems within the framework of a smart enterprise is an urgent task.

Smart factory management system with Internet of things (SFMS-IoT) has already become a stable expression and implies an inextricable connection between production and smart technologies of the IoT. The article focuses specifically on the security of the IoT, as one of the crucial components of smart manufacturing and Industry 4.0 as a whole.

The object of the study is the IoT as one of the components of the Industry 4.0 concept from the point of view of access control to objects of the information architecture of smart factory.

The subject of research is the access control system to the information environment and the architecture of the smart factory equipment, which have been combined into a single information network with the IoT.

The main goal of this work is to increase the level of risk detection of access control systems to the information infrastructure of smart factories. The goal has been achieved through the improving existing approaches to the organization of access control systems, taking into account the peculiarities of the smart industries technologies implementation, an integral component of which is the IoT with all its advantages and risks. This work is a logical continuation of research and development of a methodology for assessing the security level of access control systems using fuzzy set theory [9]; in this paper the author personally proposed the architecture of expert system rules using data from various monitoring and intrusion detection systems as input facts and confidence (reliability) coefficients for the developed rules.

The novelty of the study lies in using a combination of unstructured data from various monitoring systems, taking into account the real state of information systems over time, and combining the specified data using fuzzy sets, which allows avoiding the shortcomings of existing purely analytical approaches in assessing inherently fuzzy vulnerabilities.

The concept of smart manufacturing involves the widespread use of various sensors to continuously monitor production processes and optimize them within the overall operating model of the enterprise, which also includes logistics, sales and marketing management, information support, etc. Thus, the IoT is one of the important components of such industries in terms of receiving and transmitting the necessary data.

IoT devices are more vulnerable than conventional computers and represent a new attack vector that hackers can exploit. That is why IoT security has been a hot topic and a subject of research for many experts for many years. The paper describes the concepts behind the access control architecture and demonstrates to what extent it addresses the security, performance and extensibility concerns of public access packet switched wireless networks.

Article [10] is devoted to the questions of Wi-Fi security against scanning of rogue Wi-Fi networks and other related activities and considers the monitoring of Wi-Fi traffic effects. The unauthorized access point (AP) problem has raised more attention and resulted in obtaining wireless access without subscriber permission.

Research work [11] introduces a novel access control architecture for publicly accessible wireless overlay networks. The architecture has been designed to address the problems of ubiquitous Internet service provisioning within the city of Lancaster. The proposed access control mechanism is based on the concepts of secure user authentication, packet marking, and network-level packet filtering. The novelty of the architecture lies in its use of micro-cellular layer three networks to acquire fine grained access control in a link independent manner. The paper describes the concepts behind the access control architecture and demonstrates to what extent it addresses the security, performance and extensibility concerns of public access packet switched wireless networks.

Paper [12] describes in great detail the basic approaches and methods of machine learning in the field of cybersecurity. The authors paid special attention to the IoT and the use of artificial intelligence to reduce risks in the IoT. The work is fundamental in terms of systematization of methods and approaches of machine learning that are used in various industries to implement cybersecurity tasks.

The paper [13] presents a generic solution, which has been implemented to perform experimental analysis on Microsoft's new technology file system (NTFS) to show

how this works in practice. A simulation using expert knowledge for comparison is then performed to demonstrate how effective it is at helping the user identify potential irregular permissions.

In paper [14], trust models are proposed, which comes under the subjective trust model based on the behavior of user and service provider to calculate the trust values. The trust is fuzzy, which motivated authors to apply fuzzy logic for calculating the trust values of the cloud users and service providers in the cloud environment. They use a Mamdani fuzzy method with Gauss membership function for fuzzification and triangular membership function for defuzzification. Parameters such as performance and elasticity have been taken for trust evaluation of the resource. The attributes for calculating performance are workload and response time. For calculating elasticity, authors have taken scalability, availability, security, and usability. The fuzzy C-means clustering is applied to parameters for evaluating the trust value of users such as bad requests, bogus requests, unauthorized requests, and total requests.

IoT is undoubtedly a well-known research area. In fact, ensuring security of data exchange is among the great challenges of the IoT. In paper [15], authors endeavor to introduce a new classification of attacks in compliance with the OSI (Open Systems Interconnection) layers and the objective of security that they seek to attain in order to develop novel techniques and processes to fight against these attacks. The article has great practical value in terms of classifying the risks of the IoT.

Paper [16] describes challenges within IoT ecosystems from the perspective of cybersecurity testing along with a proposed approach to address them that will be investigated in a recently started Horizon Europe project named telemetry. The key observations regarding the design of the framework are summarized as follows. There is a need to consider the full lifecycle of IoT components — at their design time, their integration into systems, and operation of those systems. Threats and risks can propagate when components are connected together in systems — vulnerabilities in one component can affect other components in a system. IoT devices present limitations to current testing and management due to geographical distribution, opacity and limited processing power. Risk assessment fulfills an important requirement because it enables assessment of what elements are important to the system's stakeholders, how these elements might be compromised, and how the compromises may be controlled. Feedback from operational monitoring of IoT devices can inform firmware updates/patches to the devices but there is a significant challenge in rolling out these patches to multiple low-power devices geographically distributed.

The author's article develops the ideas published in this article [16] regarding the development of a methodology for assessing the risks of access control systems within the framework of the Telemetry project [17].

It should be noted that there are many published works on the topic of IoT security, which consider individual issues of information security, as it was noted earlier. From the point of view of studying the security of integrated production management systems and the IoT within smart factories, the question remains open and requires not only studying the subject of research itself, but also formulating the problem itself from the point of view of basic architectures.

In this regard, the article covers such issues as architecture and threats related to the IoT, practical coverage of approaches to building access control systems to production management systems of smart factory from the point of view of using fuzzy sets, taking into account the architectures of information systems. A fragment of the practical results of the proposed methodology was also been presented. As it noted in a purpose of article this study develops the ideas laid out in paper [9] from the point of view of the practical implementation of the developed methodology for industrial robots of smart manufacturing.

A practical approach to assessing the risk level of a smart manufacturing access control system using fuzzy set theory

Before considering the main practical results of the study, it is proposed to consider the main issues of IoT security and main properties of IoT equipment in terms of sensors and aggregators. This will allow us to identify clearly the subject of research within the broad range of IoT security issues.

IoT equipment risks

The main properties of IoT equipment in terms of sensors and aggregators [18] are shown in Fig.1.

The first group of properties relates to the transmission of information by sensors that connect the physical environment with the information environment using various principles of information acquisition and processing. Two main properties are considered:

- measurement of environmental indicators;
- performing actions based on control signals.

The second group describes the IoT properties that enable devices to interact with each other and users with devices:

- applications of IoT devices to organize their interaction with other equipment and programs, for example, application programming interface (API);
- user interface required for interaction between the user and devices, such as touch screens, haptic devices, microphones, cameras, and speakers;
- network interface, or communication channel, required to organize data exchange both within the IoT network between different devices and to transfer data to other information networks.

The third group of properties provides support for the properties of the first two groups, for example, information security, equipment management, etc.

Fig. 1

Cybersecurity risk and privacy risk are related but conceptually different. In cybersecurity, risk is about threats, namely the exploitation of vulnerabilities by threats to compromise equipment or CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability) data. In terms of privacy, it is the risks associated with the management of personal data.

As a rule, all IoT risks are considered in terms of implementing three levels of goals to reduce these risks [19].

Objective 1. Ensure the security of the device (equipment). We consider the protection of equipment from the point of view of making it impossible to use it for the purpose of carrying out attacks, for example, distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, eavesdropping on network traffic or compromising other devices in the IoT network.

IoT equipment that acts as an actuator (performs actions based on control signals) can change the physical environment and influence its state. For example, smart factories use a lot of different robots and manipulators that are connected to the IoT network. In the worst-case scenario, compromising a robot can allow an attacker to injure workers or damage equipment on production lines.

Objective 2. Ensure data security. Ensuring the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data that is collected, stored, processed or transmitted using the IoT network. The interfaces of IoT devices often provide remote access to physical systems that previously could only be reached locally. Manufacturers of such devices typically have remote access to them to provide monitoring, health control, repair, and software update functions. There is a serious problem with automatic firmware updates in the absence of customer control, which can lead to catastrophic events if the firmware does not work correctly.

Objective 3. Ensuring the protection of personal data. As IoT networks are developing, including in the social and healthcare sectors, there is a risk of loss of personally identifiable information (PII), which increases security requirements in this area.

Each goal usually relates to the previous goal and does not replace it. The implementation of these goals in order to reduce risks is been discussed in detail in [17] and includes the following areas (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

This paper considers the field of device security in terms of risk assessment from the side of the access control system to objects. The approach allows us to find out whether the existing access control system creates favorable conditions for the implementation of detected or existing exploits.

Practical application of the methodology for assessing the risk level of an access control system in the information network of smart factory

Access control policies manage the access of users or entities to system entities or subjects (devices, files, data etc.). There are several access control models that are used in information systems and provide different implementations in terms of administration and enforcement of access policies [20].

The information system of smart manufacturing could be considered from the point of view of system analysis as the interaction of subjects and objects of the system, the relationship between which is described by access control policies. Such an approach is considered in [9], where the authors propose a methodology for assessing the level of risks of an access control system using the fuzzy set apparatus, which can be used in assessing the risks of smart manufacturing.

Let us consider one of the possible variants of a generalized architecture of smart manufacturing (Fig. 3). The architecture combines smart manufacturing units such as a technological unit, a production unit, a production planning and control unit, a quality and safety control unit, etc. The diagram is rather generalized to understand the complexity of such architectures.

Fig. 3

The developed methodology [9] involves a combination of modern tools and methods for analyzing data and states of information systems in order to determine the risk level of the access control system (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

Fig. 4 describes a generalized idea of the main components of the smart factory information system, the data of which is used as input facts of the expert system for calculating the risk levels of the access control system. The relationships between objects (users) and subjects (equipment, services, etc.) are described by an access control

list (ACL). The information system is been tested both in the initial phase and during the operational phase using various monitoring and intrusion detection systems (UAM, IDS etc.). These systems, as well as the expert system, use data and rules from relevant databases and knowledge, for example, the CVE, CVSS. The knowledge base (rules) of the expert system includes more than 150 rules that allow determining the risk level of the access control system taking into account the real state of the system (user activity, system architecture, criticality of information, identified vulnerabilities, abnormal behavior of both objects and subjects, etc.) and describing it with linguistic variables. Obtaining numerical values of risks is achieved by defuzzifying the data obtained as a result of calculations.

Let us consider the specific use of the methodology for analyzing risks in terms of the access control system and vulnerabilities identified during the testing process on the example of a production line consisting of 3D printers and a number of industrial robots for processing the received goods.

The risk assessment methodology involves several possible phases or stages of its use.

- **System initiation, static indicators.** This phase occurs, as a rule, during the deployment of the information system architecture. During this phase, the risk levels of the access control system are determined and recommendations are made regarding the weaknesses in the access system.

- **Operational phase.** During the operation of the information system, the system constantly receives messages from different tools, for example, machine-learning tools, IDS regarding abnormal behavior of both objects and subjects. The methodology makes it possible to analyze the level of influence of the abnormality on the level of risks of the access control system.

- **Reorganization.** Any information system is constantly changing both from the point of view of its architecture and from the point of view of the composition of software and hardware, which requires a regular review of the risk levels of the access control management system.

Consider the initiation and operational phase, using the example of analyzing the vulnerabilities of 3-D printers and a number of industrial robots (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5

The list of vulnerabilities could be obtained using vulnerability-testing software, for example, fuzzy testing, or using the SBOM methodology. In the first case, the software provides a list of vulnerabilities directly using the center of information security benchmark libraries. In the second case, the SBOM methodology allows you to get the composition of software, services, etc. in terms of their program modules, firmware, versions, etc. and, using the CPE dictionary library, to identify existing vulnerabilities of objects. The obtained vulnerabilities in both cases allow assessing their criticality using the CVSS methodology and library.

It should be noted that Fig. 5 shows the idea of methodology implementing for the access control system risk assessment on the example of a small fragment of the architecture, which includes the following steps.

1. Identify vulnerabilities in the equipment at the software (firmware) level and obtain a CVSS vulnerability vector using appropriate tools during the initial phase.
2. Obtaining data on access control system settings with ACLs and system architecture.
3. Using a productive knowledge model implemented through rule sets using the mathematical apparatus of fuzzy logic both for initial and operational phases.

The general principles of building an expert system’s architecture for assessing the risk level of an access control system for a smart factory information system have been discussed in [9]. The architecture includes input and output data, tools and databases (libraries of standards, etc.) required to obtain input data. The input data for an expert system are discrete data from different monitoring systems, which having been used to form facts described by both fuzzy sets and discrete facts of certain system states.

The modeling was carried out using vulnerabilities common to industrial robots, 3D printers, and network equipment for the full network architecture, an example of which is shown in Fig. 6. For the created test conditions, the following results were obtained (Fig. 7) after the «detection» of these vulnerabilities.

Fig. 6

To simulate the operational phase, test data from intrusion detection systems built on the basis of machine learning were used. Cases were considered when the parameters of the equipment’s operation differed from the nominal ones, which could indicate either a failure in the system or the interception of control by an attacker.

Another variant of anomaly considered a change in user behavior, manifested in an unusual (normal) sequence of control commands, which could also indicate an attack or erroneous actions. In this case, both erroneous actions and a possible attack were considered as negative scenarios of equal importance.

Fig. 7, *a* shows the change in the risk levels of the access control system, starting from the initiation phase, when the risk levels were determined taking into account the architecture of the information system and the identified vulnerabilities of its software and hardware. Fig. 7, *b* shows the change in the risk level in case of detecting an anomaly in the behavior of system objects (in this case — robot), i.e. deviation of equipment operating parameters from nominal modes.

Fig. 7

Conclusion

The result of changing the risk levels of the access control system after testing the equipment and obtaining a list of possible vulnerabilities with the subsequent use of the mathematical apparatus of fuzzy sets allows developing advice on actions for the system administrator to be taken to reduce the identified risks.

The considered approach to risk assessment in the phase of information system deployment could also be applied to the phases of network and user reorganization. A further promising area of research is the development of more sophisticated algorithms and rule models for assessing the risk levels of an access control system during the operational phase using data from machine learning systems or IDS.

The main objectives of further development and implementation of the methodology for assessing the level of risk of the access control system are:

- improvement of the rules of the expert system in terms of introducing certainty factors for both the rules themselves and facts obtained from other systems;
- integration of all information systems (IDS, UEBA, UAM, SBOM etc.), involved in monitoring the state of subjects and objects of smart factory, in a single information environment in order to clearly synchronize in time the data that are input facts for the rules of the expert system;
- visualization of cause-and-effect diagrams to justification of the obtained risk levels and preparation of recommendations for system administrators of smart factory.

О.В. Заріцький

ЕКСПЕРТНА СИСТЕМА ОЦІНЮВАННЯ СТАНУ СИСТЕМИ КОНТРОЛЮ ДОСТУПУ ДО ІНФОРМАЦІЙНОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА РОЗУМНОГО ВИРОБНИЦТВА

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У статті розглянуто актуальні питання щодо оцінювання стану системи контролю доступу до єдиного інформаційного середовища системи керування розумним виробництвом у зв'язку з ризиками, що виникають унаслідок використання Інтернету речей як невід'ємної частини концепції Індустрії 4.0. Досліджено властивості архітектури Інтернету речей з погляду його інформаційної безпеки при інтеграції з системою керування виробництвом. Удосконалено практичний аспект методології побудови системи контролю доступу з використанням нечіткої логіки. Ця методологія продовжує попередні дослідження, в яких запропоновано й обґрунтовано ідеї щодо інтеграції різних систем моніторингу та виявлення вторгнень з метою побудови експертної системи. З погляду системного аналізу інформаційну систему проаналізовано як взаємодію суб'єктів та об'єктів системи, взаємозв'язки між якими описано політиками контролю доступу. Відповідно реальний стан об'єктів визначається архітектурою системи, вразливостями самих об'єктів та змінами стану системи в часі, що дозволяє коригувати політики доступу залежно від рівня ризиків, оцінених за вказаними даними. Методологією передбачається використання таких сучасних інструментів і програмного забезпечення, як системи виявлення вторгнень (IDS), нечітке тестування, аналітика поведінки користувачів і об'єктів (UEBA), моніторинг активності користувачів (UAM), перелік версій програмного забезпечення (SBOM), підходи машинного навчання тощо. Відповідні бібліотеки та бази даних — CIS benchmark, common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVE), common platform enumeration (CPE) dictionary та common vulnerability scoring system (CVSS) — є невід'ємною частиною методології, що дозволяє забезпечити її стандартизацію й інтеграцію з іншими підходами та методами керування й моніторингу інформаційних систем. Особливу увагу приділено виявленню вразливостей промислових роботів та оцінці їх впливу на виробничі процеси в цілому.

Ключові слова: система контролю доступу, система виявлення вторгнень, моніторинг активності користувачів, загальна система оцінки вразливостей, машинне навчання, IoT, розумна фабрика, Індустрія 4.0.

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